

THE MILITARISATION OF UZBEKISTAN'S INDUSTRY DURING THE ANTI-FASCIST WAR

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Abstract. *During the years of the war against fascism, that is, throughout the Second World War, the militarization of industry in Uzbekistan became one of the significant historical processes of the period. With the outbreak of the war, the Soviet Union was compelled to reorganize its industrial system to supply the front with essential weapons, equipment, and materials. Uzbekistan played an important role in this nationwide mobilization. After the war began in June 1941, numerous industrial enterprises, including factories, plants, and heavy industry facilities connected to armaments, were evacuated from the frontline and vulnerable regions to the interior territories of the Soviet Union. A considerable number of these enterprises, including weapons-manufacturing plants and other strategic facilities, were relocated to the cities of Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Fergana, and others. These regions were considered safe zones and strategically important for sustaining wartime production. Significant changes also occurred in Uzbekistan's light industry. The production of fabrics, footwear, clothing, and other goods was redirected to meet military needs. Key local industries, particularly the cotton and chemical industries, were reorganized to provide raw materials for military purposes. Cotton-based materials and chemical components derived from local resources were used in the production of weapons and military equipment. Foreign economic relations also shifted during the war, leading to the establishment of new enterprises responsible for manufacturing weapons, aircraft engines, tank components, and artillery parts. One of the major developments was the establishment of an aircraft engine plant in Tashkent, which specialized in producing technical equipment required at the front. Several light industry factories were also converted for military production, supplying uniforms, food products, and other essentials for frontline soldiers. Cotton, one of Uzbekistan's most valuable resources, played a crucial role in both production and processing, contributing significantly to the wartime supply chain. Throughout the war, Uzbekistan supplied the front not only with militia and special military units but also with essential materials, weapons, and equipment necessary for military operations. Local and light industries were actively engaged in numerous production and processing activities that supported the Soviet war effort. Thus, during the Second World War, Uzbekistan demonstrated substantial support through both human resources and industrial capacity. The militarized sectors of industry, including light and local industries, played an essential role in meeting the wartime military demands.*

Keywords: *World War II; front; heroism; fascism; military industry; workers of Bukhara, Tashkent, and Samarkand; industry; light industry; local industry; aviation; military uniforms; weapons; cotton industry; chemical industry; military units; aviation; tanks; tank engines; projectiles; artillery shells.*

Introduction. The war significantly reduced the resources allocated to the construction and development of light and food industry enterprises on a nationwide scale. During the war years, capital investment in these sectors decreased by approximately 60 percent compared to the

pre-war period. In 1942, the production targets for light industrial goods increased substantially. These targets were developed by taking into account the full production capacity of all enterprises that had been evacuated to Uzbekistan. The growth in production volumes required the establishment of an adequate material and technical base, as well as the supply of raw materials, fuel, and electricity for these industries.

Before the war, Uzbekistan's light industry had virtually no auxiliary facilities of its own. Metal fittings, hardware, footwear molds, chemicals, felt, and ropes all of these were imported from other regions. Since the delivery of goods from the central parts of the Soviet Union had nearly ceased in the early months of the war, it became necessary to organize the production of essential materials directly within the republic.

The republican party and soviet authorities carried out extensive work to swiftly put the evacuated equipment into operation and improve the functioning of existing enterprises. On September 2, 1942, the VI Plenum of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan (Bolsheviks) was held. The Plenum outlined concrete measures aimed at improving the performance of light and local industry enterprises. The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan (Bolsheviks) and the Council of People's Commissars assigned the regional party committees and executive committees the responsibility of ensuring the full operation of the relocated enterprises. To support this work, they allocated labor resources, construction materials, electricity, and transportation. By October 1943, more than ten enterprises had been established. Within one year, the production capacity of the local industry increased by 117 million soums, and the overall industrial capacity of the republic increased by 94 million soums. During the war years, local industry enterprises produced a wide range of consumer goods: iron beds, nets, castings, stove parts, electric stoves, electric irons, primus needles, tableware such as spoons and ladles, various scissors, tinware, baby carriages, bicycles, sleds, metal and wooden toys, meat-grinder components, barrels, furniture, various colored inks, glue, shoe cream, the cleaning powder "*Chistol*," and other products.

At the same time, these enterprises also produced military goods for the front: grenades, mortar parts, engine heaters, bronze components, and other items. For example, the Chkalov Metal Goods Plant, which had previously produced various consumer products such as buckets, basins, small ovens, meat grinders, metal toys, children's bicycles and carriages, and sleds, switched to the production of military equipment, various spare parts, mortars, and other war supplies at the outbreak of the war. Much of this output was produced in cooperation with evacuated enterprises. The plant's gross output increased from 1.8 million soums in 1940 to 5.8 million soums in 1943, a growth of 322.2 percent. At the same time, the plant continued manufacturing consumer goods such as table spoons and tea spoons, forks, braziers, lighters, and shoe nails, which were in high demand during wartime.

The Tashkent Wood-Processing Plant, which had previously produced a variety of household furniture, shifted to fulfilling special military orders. At the same time, workers began producing children's toys and clay household items using waste materials and fuel made from sawdust. The plant's gross output increased from 1.2 million soums in 1940 to 5 million soums in 1943. During the war, the plant was supplied with additional equipment, which made it possible to organize an assembly shop and adopt a conveyor-based production method. The cast-iron goods plant, which before the war had manufactured cast-iron household items, electric stoves, electric irons, and locks, and had also been involved in boiler construction, played an important role in restoring evacuated enterprises. The workers learned how to repair boiler systems, manufacture

mechanical parts, and assemble cupola furnaces. In addition to these tasks, the plant also produced various components for major construction projects such as the Fergana Canal, the Bekabad Metallurgical Plant, the Angren Coal Works, and the Farhad Hydroelectric Station. The plant's gross output increased from 0.6 million soums in 1940 to 1.7 million soums in 1943. The wagon-building plant faced extremely difficult conditions. It underwent nearly two years of reconstruction and equipment installation. This plant had the capacity to produce up to ten thousand horse-drawn military wagons annually. However, throughout the war, there was a severe shortage of special timber and certain metal profiles, which had previously been supplied from other regions of the Soviet Union.

As a result, wagon production suffered; in 1943, only one thousand wagons were produced. Due to the critical shortage of raw materials, the plant was forced to shift to manufacturing other products and performing repair work. Similar circumstances could be observed in many other local industry enterprises throughout the republic. During the war years, soap production, textile and fabric manufacturing, felt and footwear production, wool processing, the chemical and haberdashery industries, as well as salt extraction, experienced substantial development. Repair workshops for carts, metal goods, and household services expanded considerably. The labor heroism and selfless dedication of workers in Uzbekistan's light and local industries enabled continuous increases in production for both the front and the home front, while also allowing them to fulfill other important state tasks. As a result, by 1945, Uzbekistan ranked first among the Central Asian republics in the production of heavy leather goods and second in the production of hosiery and footwear. Statistical data also show that many of the above-mentioned types of products were manufactured exclusively in Uzbekistan, while in some other republics, production in these sectors had declined.

Uzbekistan's light industry made a significant contribution to the victory over Nazi Germany. New branches of the industry, spinning, knitting, and yarn-spinning, were established during the war years. Due to the reorganization of several sewing factories, Uzbekistan became a major sewing-industry center. The production of sewing goods increased by 1.5 times in 1944 compared to 1940, reaching 107 million square decimeters. In 1943, the People's Commissariat of Light Industry of the republic supervised 37 enterprises; by 1945, this number exceeded 50. The number of enterprises in the local industry also surpassed ten. During the war, the people of Tashkent alone supplied the army with 800,000 *gymnastyorka* shirts, 2,636,000 quilted jackets (*telogreyka*), and 2,221,200 pairs of soldiers' boots.

Uzbekistan's share in the total potential of the Soviet Union's light industry increased significantly from 0.63 percent in 1940 to 9.3 percent in 1941. The republic's light and local industries played an important and honorable role in contributing to the common national victory over the Nazi invaders. From all of the above, it is necessary to draw the following conclusion: the labor of light-industry workers during the war years cannot be evaluated solely based on whether they fulfilled or failed to fulfill state production plans. Their work must be assessed with full consideration of the difficult objective conditions under which they labored, as well as the quantity and significance of the products they produced. Such an assessment reflects their true contribution to the nationwide victory over Nazi fascism and acknowledges their devotion, courage, and tireless effort in securing the freedom and independence of our Motherland.

Analysis of Literature and Methodological Foundations

The years of the Second World War represent a critical period in the socio-economic history of Uzbekistan, during which the republic played a significant role not only through human resources, but also through the rapid mobilization of its industrial potential. Several industrial enterprises evacuated from the western regions of the Soviet Union, primarily from Ukraine, Russia, and other frontline territories, were relocated to Uzbekistan. This large-scale evacuation served as an important catalyst for the accelerated development of the republic's industrial infrastructure.

The impact of the war on Uzbekistan's industrial sector was multidimensional. On the one hand, the wartime economy demanded substantial restructuring, technological adaptation, and the expansion of production lines. On the other hand, the region witnessed the emergence of new industries and the modernization of existing facilities. Although cotton growing remained the dominant sector of the Uzbek SSR's economy during the war, several industrial branches such as chemical production, metallurgy, cotton processing, and textile manufacturing experienced notable growth. A significant portion of Uzbekistan's industrial capacity was redirected toward meeting wartime needs. The republic became a major center for the production of military equipment, uniforms, and essential food supplies. The rapid development of the energy sector, including the construction of new power facilities, further strengthened the industrial foundation of the region. By the end of the war, Uzbekistan had not only increased its manufacturing output but had also adopted new technologies that contributed to the diversification of its industrial structure. The contribution of the light industry to the wartime economy deserves particular emphasis. New branches such as spinning, knitting, and yarn production were established, while several sewing factories were reorganized to operate under wartime conditions. As a result, Uzbekistan transformed into one of the key textile-production centers of the Soviet Union. In 1944, the production of garments increased by 1.5 times compared to 1940. The number of enterprises under the jurisdiction of the People's Commissariat of Light Industry of the Uzbek SSR rose from 37 in 1943 to more than 50 by 1945, with an additional 10 enterprises functioning within the local industry system.

The scale of wartime production in Tashkent alone illustrates the significance of Uzbekistan's contribution: laborers manufactured approximately 800,000 gymnastyorka shirts, 2,636,000 quilted jackets (telogreyka), and 2,221,200 pairs of military footwear for the Red Army. Consequently, the share of Uzbekistan in the overall production capacity of the Soviet Union's light industry expanded sharply from 0.63% in 1940 to 9.3% by 1941. The reorganization of textile enterprises and the establishment of new production lines enabled Uzbekistan to grow into a prominent textile-manufacturing hub within the USSR. By 1944, textile output had reached 107 million square decimeters, an increase of 1.5 times compared to pre-war levels. The data presented above demonstrate that the labor of workers in light and local industries during the war must be evaluated not only through the lens of plan fulfillment. Rather, it should be assessed by considering the extraordinary conditions under which production took place and the critical importance of the output they achieved. Such an approach reflects the true extent of the heroic labor, resilience, and dedication exhibited by industrial workers during wartime. Their contribution was essential to the overall victory over fascism and played a significant role in safeguarding the freedom and independence of the homeland.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

June 22, 1941, is remembered by all humanity as one of the darkest days in world history. On this day, the German fascist invaders treacherously crossed the western borders of the Soviet Union and launched a large-scale offensive. As a result, the people of the USSR, including Uzbekistan, were compelled to rise and fight against fascist aggression. At the onset of the war, the Soviet Union was not fully prepared for such a sudden and massive attack. Taking advantage of this situation, the enemy quickly occupied the frontier territories and advanced deep into the country. In these extremely difficult circumstances, the government organized a nationwide struggle against fascism and was able to instill confidence among the population that victory was attainable. On June 30, 1941, the State Defense Committee was established and entrusted with significant responsibilities. By exercising its extensive powers, the Committee directed the transition of the national economy to a wartime regime, ensured the mobilization of the working masses, and reorganized production processes. These measures played a decisive role in securing the ultimate victory.

One of the most important historical developments during the Second World War was the relocation and militarization of industrial production in Uzbekistan. With the outbreak of war, the Soviet Union was forced to reorganize its industry to meet the enormous demand for weapons, ammunition, equipment, and other supplies for the front. Uzbekistan made a substantial contribution to this process. After June 1941, a large number of industrial enterprises, particularly those related to heavy industry and defense production, were evacuated from war zones and transferred to Uzbekistan. Many strategic factories, including weapon-manufacturing plants and other critical facilities, were relocated to the cities of Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Fergana, and other regions of the republic, which were considered secure territories far from the front line.

This evacuation laid the foundation for the rapid industrial development of Uzbekistan during the war. Significant changes also took place within the light industry sector. The production of textiles, footwear, various types of clothing, and other consumer goods was reorganized to meet military needs. Local industrial sectors such as cotton processing and chemical production were adapted for wartime purposes. Cotton-derived raw materials and chemicals were used to produce essential items for military equipment and ammunition. Wartime economic conditions also reshaped Uzbekistan's external and internal industrial relations. New enterprises producing weapon components, aviation engines, tank and artillery parts were established. In Tashkent, an aviation engine plant was opened, specializing in the production of vital machinery for the front. Additionally, numerous light industry factories were converted to a wartime regime, producing uniforms, food supplies, and other essential goods for soldiers. Cotton remained one of Uzbekistan's most valuable resources. During the war, cotton production and processing served not only civilian needs but also military objectives. Uzbekistan played a crucial role in supplying cotton fiber and other raw materials necessary for manufacturing wartime goods and equipment.

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